

Whole genome sequence of *Streptomyces albidoflavus* strain AS2: insights into nematicidal potential against root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.)

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Abstract

Streptomyces albidoflavus is a soil-dwelling actinobacterium widely recognized for its prolific production of bioactive secondary metabolites with antimicrobial and biocontrol properties. In this study, we report the whole genome sequence data of *S. albidoflavus* strain AS2, an endophyte *actinomycetota* isolated from *Alyssum spinosum* (L.) in the Oukaimeden region of Morocco. The genome was sequenced using NovaSeq 6000 technology, yielding 1,631,563 high-quality paired-end reads with a mean coverage depth of 102.094×. De novo assembly process conducted using SPAdes resulted in 97 contigs totalling 7,239,030 bp with a GC content of 73.5%. Genome annotation using Prokka identified 6449 genes, including 6263 protein-coding sequences and 21 rRNAs genes. The genetic sequence has been deposited in NCBI GenBank under BioProject accession number [PRJNA1259013](#). This valuable genetic resource will provide a basis for understanding the biosynthetic and nematicidal potential of *S. albidoflavus* AS2, and support further functional studies to explore its application in sustainable agricultural pest management.

Introduction

The genus *Streptomyces* comprises of Gram-positive, filamentous bacteria renowned for their prolific capacity to synthesize a diverse array of secondary metabolites, including antibiotics, antifungals, immunosuppressants, and enzymes. These bacteria are considered one of the most prolific sources of natural products, with approximately 100,000 known antibiotic compounds, accounting for 70-80% of bioactive compounds, with diverse biological activity (Ait Barka et al. 2016; Donald et al. 2022; Harir et al. 2018).

Among *Streptomyces* species, *S. albidoflavus* has gained attention for its potential role in plant protection. This soil-dwelling bacterium suppresses plant pathogens through multiple mechanisms, including the synthesis of diverse bioactive compounds (Carlucci et al. 2022; Du et al. 2022; Yao et al. 2021). Despite these promising biocontrol traits, the molecular basis of its pesticidal action remains poorly explored. This is particularly significant for root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.), which rank among the most devastating plant-parasitic nematodes affecting crop productivity worldwide (Elhady et al. 2024; Jones et al. 2013; Phani, Khan, and Dutta 2021).

Recent study has previously demonstrated significant *in vitro* nematicidal activity against *Meloidogyne* spp., the root-knot nematodes, highlighting its potential as a biocontrol agent (Azlay et al. 2024). However, comprehensive genomic data for this strain have not yet been reported, limiting efforts to identify biosynthetic gene clusters and molecular determinants responsible for its antiparasitic properties. In this context, we conducted whole-genome sequencing and annotation of *S. albidoflavus* strain AS2 to characterize its genetic repertoire, emphasizing genes associated with the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites that may exhibit nematicidal activity. The availability of this genome resource will facilitate future functional genomics studies and promote the development of sustainable biocontrol strategies in agriculture.

Material and methods

Bacterial isolation and characterization

The AS2 isolate is an endophytic actinobacterium isolated from *Alyssum spinosum* (L.) collected in the Oukaimeden region (31.198768, -7.871709, Morocco). This isolated strain is a part of the microbial collection maintained by the Laboratory of Water Sciences, Microbial Biotechnologies and Natural Resources Sustainability, within the Unit of Microbial Biotechnology, Agrosciences and Environment at Cadi Ayyad University, Marrakech, Morocco. The isolate was initially identified as *Streptomyces violascens* based on 16S rRNA gene sequencing (Azlay et al. 2024). However, subsequent whole-genome sequencing and comprehensive phylogenomic analysis revealed that the strain is more accurately classified as *Streptomyces albidoflavus*. This demonstrates the higher resolution and accuracy of genome-based approaches compared to 16S rRNA gene analysis alone, particularly for closely related *Streptomyces* species that often exhibit high 16S rRNA sequence similarity but can be reliably differentiated using whole-genome data.

Microbial culture and genomic DNA extraction

For genomic DNA extraction, AS2 was cultivated in Bennett's broth (glucose 10 g/L, yeast extract 1 g/L, beef extract 1 g/L, peptone 2 g/L; pH 7.2) at 30 °C (Azlay et al. 2024). High-quality genomic DNA was extracted by lysing 5 to 40 µL of cell suspension in TE buffer containing lysozyme (0.1 mg/mL) and RNase A (0.1 mg/mL) with incubation at 37°C for 25 minutes. Proteinase K (0.1 mg/mL) and SDS (0.5% v/v) were then added, followed by incubation at 65°C for 5 minutes to digest proteins and facilitate lysis. Genomic DNA was purified using SPRI magnetic beads and resuspended in EB buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0). The extracted DNA was quantified using the Quant-iT dsDNA HS assay on an Eppendorf AF2200 plate reader and diluted as needed for downstream applications.

Whole genome sequencing

Genomic DNA sequences from *Streptomyces albidoflavus*, strain AS2, was sequenced by MicrobesNG service run within the University of Birmingham (<https://microbesng.com>). DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with modifications: the input DNA was doubled, and the PCR elongation time was extended to 45 seconds. DNA quantification and library preparation were carried out using a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina

NovaSeq 6000 sequencer (Illumina, San Diego, USA) with a 250 bp paired-end read configuration.

Quality control and genome assembly

Raw reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic v0.30 software (Bolger, Lohse, and Usadel 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15 to remove adapters and low-quality regions. De novo gene assembly was performed using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al. 2012), generating contigs suitable for downstream annotation.

Genome annotation and feature prediction

Automated genome annotation was performed using Prokka v1.14.5 (Seemann 2014), which predicts coding sequences (CDSs), tRNAs, rRNAs, tmRNAs, and CRISPR arrays using curated databases (UniProt, RefSeq). Annotation revealed 6,509 genes, including 6,355 protein-coding sequences, 69 tRNAs, 21 rRNAs, 2 tmRNAs, and 6 CRISPR regions. The coding density was estimated at 87.9%, consistent with actinobacterial genomes.

Data availability

The assembled genome has been deposited in the NCBI GenBank under BioProject ID [PRJNA1259013](#), with the associated accession numbers [JBNQWS000000000](#) (assembly) and [SRR33434693](#) (raw reads). This version represents the first draft genome of *S. albidoflavus* strain AS2.

Results

Genome assembly overview

The Illumina NovaSeq 6000 sequencing of *Streptomyces albidoflavus* strain AS2 yielded a total of 1,631,563 paired-end reads, which were quality-trimmed using Trimmomatic and assembled using SPAdes v3.7. The high-quality de novo assembly produced 97 contigs, with a total genome size of 7239030 bp and an average GC content of 73.5%—a typical feature of *Streptomyces* species. The assembly had an N50 contig size of 164,170 bp, with the largest contig measuring 411,240 bp, and an average coverage depth of 102.094×, confirming the completeness and robustness of the assembly. An overview of genome statistics is summarized in table 1.

Annotation and Genomic features

Automated annotation using Prokka v1.14.5 identified 6,449 genes, comprising:

- 6356 protein-coding sequences (CDSs)
- 69 transfer RNAs (tRNAs)
- 21 ribosomal RNAs (5S, 16S, and 23S rRNAs)
- 5 complete rRNAs (5S and 16S)
- 16 partial rRNAs (5S, 16S and 23S)
- 2 transfer-messenger RNAs (tmRNAs)
- 3 additional non-coding RNAs
- 6 clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeat (CRISPR) arrays.

The coding density was 87.9%, with no ambiguous nucleotide regions (N-bases) detected, reflecting a well-resolved and high-quality genome. The presence of CRISPR arrays may

suggest adaptive immunity mechanisms against phages or plasmids, often relevant in microbial competition within the rhizosphere.

Table 1: Characteristics of whole genome assembly of *Streptomyces albidoflavus*, strain AS2 isolated from *Alyssum spinosum*, Oukaimeden, Morocco.

Total genome size	7239030
Reads	
Number of reads	1631563
Median size	726
Mean Coverage	102.094
Contigs	
Number	97
Number (>= 1k bp)	72
Total length (pb)	7239030
Largest contig	411240
Total length	7232377
GC (%)	73.5
N50 contig number (bp)	164170
Coding ratio	0.879
N-ratio	0
tRNA	69
tm RNA	2
r RNA	21
Nc RNA	3
Pseudo genes (total)	93
CRISPR	6
Total CDs	6356
Gens (coding)	6263
Genes (Total)	6449
Genes (RNA)	93
BioProject	PRJNA1259013
Biosmaple	SAMN48346246
GenBank accession (reads)	SRR33434693
GenBank accession (assembly)	JBNQWS000000000

Biosynthetic and functional potential

The complete genome sequencing of the strain revealed a sophisticated genetic architecture comprising 6,449 total genes, including 6,356 coding sequences (CDS) functionally annotated protein-coding genes that form the core of its metabolic potential. The genomic landscape features 95 RNA genes (69 tRNAs, 21 rRNAs, 2 tmRNAs, and 3 ncRNAs) ensuring efficient translation and precise gene regulation, complemented by 6 CRISPR arrays providing adaptive immunity. This genomic profile underscores the presence of numerous genes potentially involved in biocontrol mechanisms. Such a diverse genetic repertoire likely encodes various biosynthetic pathways responsible for producing bioactive metabolites that contribute to plant pathogen suppression. Particularly noteworthy is the harmonious integration of tRNAs, rRNAs maintaining proteome integrity, ncRNAs/tmRNAs, optimizing stress responses, and defense systems- CRISPR, which collectively establish *S. albidoflavus* AS2 as a genetically robust and

biotechnologically promising platform for developing novel biocontrol solutions. This meticulously annotated genetic repertoire demonstrates exceptional biosynthetic capacity, with the protein-coding genes encoding diverse secondary metabolite pathways responsible for the strain's experimentally confirmed nematicidal activity. Furthermore, these findings provide genetic evidence supporting the previously observed nematicidal activity of *S. albidoflavus* strain AS2 and reinforce its potential as a source of novel biocontrol agents (Azlay et al. 2024).

Discussion

The present study provides the first draft genome sequence of *Streptomyces albidoflavus* strain AS2, an endophytic actinobacterium isolated from *Alyssum spinosum* (L) in a mountainous Moroccan ecosystem. This strain has previously demonstrated significant nematicidal activity against *Meloidogyne* spp. under *in vitro* conditions (Azlay et al., 2024), which prompted its genomic characterization to explore the underlying genetic basis of its biocontrol potential.

Genomic quality and taxonomic features

The assembled genome, totalling 7.2 Mbp with a high GC content (73.5%), is consistent with known *Streptomyces* genomes (Ait Barka et al. 2016; Donadio, Monciardini, and Sosio 2007). The assembly metrics—particularly the N50 value (164,2 kbp) and low number of contigs (97)—indicate a high-quality draft, further supported by the absence of ambiguous nucleotides and a high coding density (87.9%). These features ensure reliability for downstream functional and comparative genomic analyses.

Endophytic lifestyle and adaptive traits

As an endophytic strain, AS2 may possess specialized traits enabling colonization of internal plant tissues and interaction with the host immune system. Comparative genomic studies of endophytic versus soil-dwelling *Streptomyces* spp. have highlighted differences in genes associated with oxidative stress resistance, secretion systems, and plant hormone modulation (Gayrard et al. 2023; Malfent et al. 2024; Veilumuthu et al. 2024). Functional annotation of the AS2 genome may uncover similar adaptations, reinforcing its candidacy as a biocontrol endophyte. In addition, the detection of CRISPR arrays also suggests active genome defense mechanisms that could confer ecological advantages in competitive rhizosphere or endospheric environments, where horizontal gene transfer and phage predation are common.

Contribution to biocontrol research and agricultural applications

The genome of *S. albidoflavus* AS2 enriches the current genomic landscape of actinobacteria with biopesticidal potential and offers a platform for the discovery of novel bioactive metabolites. Moreover, the genome will facilitate targeted mutagenesis, heterologous expression, and transcriptomic studies to validate nematicidal gene function. Such approaches are essential for the development of eco-friendly biopesticide formulations compatible with sustainable agricultural systems and Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies, particularly in the context of nematode suppression (Gayrard et al. 2023; Jönsson et al. 2025).

Challenges and future directions

While this study provides valuable genomic data, functional validation of candidate genes—through gene knockout, metabolite profiling, or RNA-seq—remains necessary to confirm their

roles in nematicidal activity. Furthermore, *in vivo* assays under greenhouse or field conditions are needed to assess the biocontrol efficacy of AS2 in real agroecosystems. Expanding this research to include comparative genomics with other nematicidal *Streptomyces* strains may help identify conserved genetic determinants and metabolic signatures specific to nematode suppression.

Conclusion

The draft genome of *Streptomyces albidoflavus* strain AS2 provides crucial insights into its biosynthetic and biocontrol potential. The presence of key gene clusters associated with secondary metabolism and hydrolytic activity supports its previously demonstrated nematicidal effect. This genomic resource lays the groundwork for future functional studies and opens new perspectives for the development of biological control agents targeting root-knot nematodes in sustainable agriculture.

Acknowledgments

The bacterial strain sequencing was supported by the GetGenome project and The Sainsbury Laboratory (Norwich, UK), with support from the Gatsby Charitable Foundation and the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC).

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